

TECHNOLOGY OF WORKING UNDER VIBRATORY STRESS: VIBRAFORMING

Frank Michaud
Dias Industrie
43 Avenue de la Côte d'Argent
33380 MARCHEPRIME-FRANCE

Vibraforming can be considered as a real technology and involves the vibration setting of very different elements. According to the nature of the products and the characteristics of the vibration applied, it is possible to:

- homogenize mixtures,
- improve the properties of composite material by acting at following levels:
 - degassing,
 - interface,
 - compaction,
 - distribution,
 - impregnation,
- compact the material,
- alter the rheology,
- use new materials,
- transport the material,
- maintain elements in suspension.

Both the frequency and amplitude of vibration are determined by first recording and analyzing the mechanical properties of the components in isolation (and if necessary those of the container), which are subjected to a vibration of continuously varying frequency.

That is why the laboratory has important investigational facilities which allow it to study and record the properties of materials within an automatically controlled frequency range of 0 to 50 000 Hz.

In practical terms, the vibration is transmitted either by the container to which one or various sources of inter-synchronous vibrations are directly connected, or by an adapted system in direct contact with the constituents.

The following application examples give further details about the phenomenon induced by the vibration setting of various materials but are not an exhaustive list of the possible applications.

1)- Vibration applied to one or more constituents.

a)- Powder mixtures.

A mixture is obtained through a flow generated by interparticle rebounds, induced by a vibration of resonance frequency and amplitude are determined.

The flow can be generated through upward vertical motion from the centre to the top of the container or from the bottom to the centre.

It creates a homogeneous mixture of constituents of different densities, granulometries and in different proportions.

In comparison with the mechanical constraints applied to the materials when they are put into operation, the structure and nature of the constituents are respected by the vibration. This is a tremendous advantage with a mixture of fragile microspheres, with unstable components (explosives, etc.).

The technology makes it possible to mix products with different electrostatic charges. It presents the same advantages as a fluid bed, i.e. each particle covers the same distance.

Moreover, they all have the same contact with the container. The electrostatic charge can thus be transferred from the sides to the powder and can inverse the charge if necessary.

b)- Making composite materials (reinforcers, fillers/matrix).

The general procedure is as follows:

The elements in the dry phase like fillers, reinforcers, thermoplastics, etc., are vibrated at a determined resonance frequency (in opposition of phase to the mould) in order to homogenize and dilate the mixture.

Vibration is maintained during injection in order to impregnate the dry phase, to homogenize and degas the mixture.

The so-called "anti-resonance" frequency is then applied (in phase with the mould) to compress the mixture, creating links between the constituents. Vibration is maintained until the polymerizable matrix jellifies.

The resulting composite material has a structure which is quite free of air, compact, and dense, and the quality of the dry phase/matrix interface is improved.

Examples of applications:

Fibre type composites, solid matrix constituents (e.g. thermoplastics) / vibration causes transversal dilatation and spacing of the fibrils which make up the strands of the fibre so that the powder grains come to rest in the spaces made. In this way, preimpregnated dry structures can be produced.

Matrix type composites (thermoplastic or duroplastic) / short fibres. Vibration not only causes better impregnation, it also causes deflocculation which then leads to the distribution and isotropic orientation of the fibres in the volume of the matrix.

Composites with high filler contents: resin microspheres- type syntactic foam (carbon, glass, etc.). Making microspheres vibrate at a resonance frequency produces expansion which leads to an ordered arrangement in the material. The mixture is then compressed by vibration at another appropriate frequency. At this point a very clear densification may be observed that is not present in an unvibrated product.

Many other materials, such as sand, can be compacted in the same way.

Resin is then injected while the vibration is maintained until jellification.

With this method the amount of filler can be appreciably increased (up to 85% of volume) so as to obtain a material with a very low density (as little as 0.2) and improved mechanical properties owing to degassing, the quality of the interfaces and homogeneity of the mixture.

c)- Fluidification of resin.

The vibration of a thixotropic or viscous material at a given frequency will reduce viscosity in the same way as would the application of calorific energy.

d)- Orientation of reinforcers.

The orientation of conductive short fibres in a matrix is achieved by applying a magnetic field to the vibrated mixture.

By modifying the rheology of the matrix, vibration facilitates fibre movement. In this way, anisotropic materials are obtained which, in comparison to unvibrated samples, show an appreciably higher percentage of parallel fibres. The reinforcer/matrix ratio of these materials may be increased.

2)- Vibration applied to long fibres.

The impregnation of woven or non-woven fibres by a liquid matrix is always difficult owing to the occlusions of air present in the basic fibres which impede the wetting of the matrix.

Vibration applied directly to the fibres or transmitted through a specially adapted container generates:

- a dilation of the reinforcers which facilitates impregnation of the depths of the basic fibres.

- a migration of the resin which has been deposited on the various folds towards the surface (lay-up).

As well as an appreciable improvement in quality, vibration also eases impregnation of difficult materials such as multidirectional fabrics, thick complexes, knitted structures, etc.